

Fluid Mechanics, and Its Quantum Developments and Applications

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Abstract:

Based on the known theories of fluid mechanics, we research the new quantum fluid mechanics by operator method. Further, we discuss its various developments combined the extensive quantum theory and other theories. Finally, we search possible applications in some aspects: in biology many systems are fluids; in astronomy binary stars, the density wave theory and evolutionary direction on spiral galaxies, and sunspot are researched; in geosciences earthquake, formation of basin and hydrocarbon layer are proposed;

in social sciences the social hydrodynamics and corresponding waves and tides, the social synergetics, corruption, etc., are discussed.

Keywords: *fluid mechanics, quantum, operator, development, application, the extensive quantum theory, biology, astronomy, geosciences, social sciences.*

Introduction

Fluid mechanics investigates generally the motion and equilibrium of fluids (liquids and gases). It includes hydrodynamics, and is applied to physical chemistry, plasma physics, meteorology, biology, biomedicine, and so on. Since the Earth is surrounded by air and water, geosciences are also associated closely with fluid mechanics.

Conventional quantum fluids include boson fluids and fermion fluids, and the corresponding transport theory and Onsager relation (Reichl, 1980). So far the quantum fluid mechanics research mainly some special aspects, for example, plasma, superfluid of ultralow temperatures, etc (Putterman, 1974; Forster, 1975).

Recently, developing numerical methods to simulate efficiently nonlinear fluid dynamics on universal quantum computers is a challenging

problem. Zylberman, et al. (2022), generalized that the Madelung transform is defined to solve quantum relativistic charged fluid equations interacting with external electromagnetic forces via the Dirac equation. In universal quantum computers, a variant of this algorithm is proposed to implement simulations using current noisy intermediate scale quantum (NISQ) devices in the case of homogeneous external forces, hydrodynamics can be simulated on NISQs, and opens the door to simulating other fluids, including plasmas, with more general quantum walks and quantum automata.

It is known that the conduction electrons in metals behave very similar to gaseous plasmas and can be well treated as an electron gas. Conventional plasmas found naturally in the visible universe (e.g., the Sun's environment, interplanetary and intergalactic media, etc.) or created in the laboratory (e.g., discharge experiments, etc.) are ionized gases in which the charged particles (electrons and different ions)

move under the influence of long-range electromagnetic forces. Although, the individual particles obey the laws of quantum mechanics, the wave nature of the particles has practically no effect on the collective motion in the case of classical plasmas, due to the large inter-particle distances, and the plasma can adequately be described by classical dynamical laws in the framework of Newtonian mechanics and Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) statistics (Tsubota, et al. 2012).

Quantum plasma physics is a rapidly evolving research field with a very inter-disciplinary scope of potential applications, ranging from nano-scale science in condensed matter to the vast scales of astrophysical objects. Its theoretical description relies on various approaches, microscopic or macroscopic models. In classical plasmas, further simplifications are achieved by a transition to hydrodynamic equations. In book *Complex Plasmas: Scientific Challenges and Technological Opportunities* (Bonitz, et al. 2013), Khan and Bonitz (2013) seared the main concepts of quantum hydrodynamics (QHD), and analyzed its validity range and main limitations. The basic concepts and formulation of particle-particle interactions are reviewed, indicating their possible consequences in quantum many-body problems.

Now quantum hydrodynamics in superfluid helium and atomic Bose-Einstein condensates (BECs) has been one of the most important topics in low temperature physics. In these systems, a macroscopic wave function appears because BES creates quantized vortices. Turbulence consisting of quantized vortices is called quantum turbulence (QT).

Alexeev (2015) published a book *Unified Non-Local Theory of Transport Processes*. It includes 12 Chapters (Theory of Generalized Hydrodynamic Equations, Quantum Non-Local Hydrodynamics, Non-Local Quantum Hydrodynamics in the Theory of Plasmoids and the Atom Structure, Physics of a Weakly Ionized Gas, Generalized Boltzmann Equation in the Theory of the Rarefied Gases and Liquids, Strict Theory of Turbulence and Some Applications of the Generalized Hydrodynamic Theory,

Astrophysical Applications, The Generalized Relativistic Kinetic Hydrodynamic Theory, and so on) and 10 Appendixes (Using of Curvilinear Coordinates in the Generalized Hydrodynamic Theory, Characteristic Scales in Plasma Physics, Some Integral Calculations in the Generalized Navier-Stokes Approximation, To the Non-Local Theory of Variable Stars, etc). Further, Alexeev reviewed the main principles of the unified nonlocal theory of transport processes. Its conclusions are: 1. Madelung's quantum hydrodynamics is equivalent to the Schrödinger equation (SE) and leads to the description of the quantum particle evolution in the form of the Euler equation and continuity equation. The quantum Euler equation contains additional potential of nonlocal origin. SE is the consequence of the Liouville equation as result of the local approximation of nonlocal equations. 2. Generalized Boltzmann physical kinetics leads to the strict approximation of nonlocal effects in space and time and in the local limit leads to parameter τ , which on the quantum level corresponds to the uncertainty principle "time-energy." 3. The nonlocal physical kinetics contains the SE as a deep particular case of the generalized Boltzmann physical kinetics and therefore of nonlocal hydrodynamics.

Physical systems made of many interacting quantum particles can often be described by Euler hydrodynamic equations in the limit of long wavelengths and low frequencies. Now a classical hydrodynamic framework is called generalized hydrodynamics (GHD), was found for quantum integrable models in one spatial dimension. It describes quantum fluctuations of nonequilibrium systems (Ruggiero, et al. 2020). Durey and Bush (2020) proposed the hydrodynamic quantum field theory. Further, Suárez-Forero, et al. (2020) considered the hydrodynamic quantum field theory as a model of quantum dynamics inspired by de Broglie and informed by the hydrodynamic pilot-wave system discovered by Couder and Fort. They recast the particle dynamics in terms of an integro-differential trajectory equation, which guided by analogous theoretical descriptions of the hydrodynamic system, and provide the

foundation for subsequent theoretical investigations of hydrodynamic quantum field theory, including the stability analysis of various dynamical states. Quantum hydrodynamics comes from superfluid, superconductivity, semiconductor and so on. Quantum hydrodynamic model describes Helium II superfluid, Bose–Einstein condensation in inert gas, dissipative perturbation of Hamilton–Jacobi system, amplitude and dissipative perturbation of Eikonal quantum wave and so on. Based on the above facts, Boling Guo (2023) collected and collated the data of quantum hydrodynamic equations, and studied the concerning mathematical problems. In this book the main contents are: the derivation and mathematical models of complex quantum hydrodynamic equations, global existence of weak solutions to the compressible quantum hydrodynamic equations, existence of finite energy weak solutions of inviscid quantum hydrodynamic equations, non-isentropic quantum Navier-Stokes equations with cold pressure, boundary problem of compressible quantum Euler-Poisson equations, asymptotic limit to the bipolar quantum hydrodynamic equations. In this paper, we research the quantum fluid mechanics by operator method, and search possible applications of fluid mechanics.

Hydrodynamics and Its Quantum Developments

In 1927 E. Madelung published “Quantum theory in fluid mechanics”, so that $\psi = \alpha e^{i\beta}$ corresponds to wave, and α, β are real functions, α^2 interpreted as fluid density, then β is proportional to the fluid velocity potential, thus they substitute into Schrödinger equation. Let $\varphi = -(\hbar/m)\beta$, so this derive the virtual and real part:

$$\nabla(\alpha^2 \nabla \varphi) + \frac{\partial \alpha^2}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \varphi)^2 + \frac{V}{m} - \frac{\nabla^2 \alpha}{\alpha} \frac{\hbar^2}{2m^2} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Both are the same as the dynamical equations of the ideal fluid. $\alpha^2(\varphi)$ corresponds to the density of the fluid (the velocity potential). $\nabla \varphi = V$ so

$$\nabla \frac{v^2}{2} = V \times \text{rot} V + (V \text{grad}) V \quad (3)$$

Such quantum mechanics becomes the fluid dynamics of the continuous distribution of mass and charge. It is formally similar to the hydrodynamic equation of an inviscid fluid with irrotational motion under a conservative force. This may reflect the properties of the electrons and the particles, etc. This so-called Madelung quantum hydrodynamics, and is a new stochastic interpretation of quantum mechanics as the background.

It may be developed and corrected, let $\psi = \alpha e^{i\beta}$ so

$$\psi' = (\alpha' + i\alpha\beta') e^{i\beta}, \quad (4a)$$

$$\psi'' = (\alpha'' - \alpha\beta'^2 + 2i\alpha'\beta' + i\alpha\beta'') e^{i\beta} \quad (4b)$$

They substitute into Klein-Gordon (KG) equation, and obtain:

$$\alpha - \alpha(\partial_\mu \beta)^2 - m^2 \alpha = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\beta + \frac{2}{\alpha} \partial_\mu \alpha \partial_\mu \beta = 0 \quad (6)$$

They substitute into Dirac equations, and obtain:

$$\gamma_\mu \partial_\mu \alpha + m \alpha = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\gamma_\mu \alpha \partial_\mu \beta = 0 \quad (8)$$

α, β are separated, (7) (8) are Dirac equations and Weyl equations, respectively. (8) substitutes into (5)(6), i.e., KG and Maxwell equations. These correspond to $W^\pm - Z^0(\pi)$, photon (Goldstone particle), e-leptons (p-baryon) and neutrino equations.

Based on various equations of general fluid mechanics and their operators, we research the general quantum fluid mechanics.

Basic laws are: 1. The continuity equation (conservation of matter) of fluids is:

$$\frac{\partial j_\mu}{\partial x_\mu} = \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla(\rho v) = 0 \quad (9)$$

Here $\rho = c\psi^* \psi$. 2. Conservation of energy. 3. Momentum equation. For ideal fluid flow, Euler equation is:

$$F = \frac{dV}{dt} + \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p \quad (10)$$

First, it must introduce an operator of velocity V:

$$V_\mu = \frac{p_\mu}{\rho} = -i \frac{\hbar}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu} \quad (11)$$

The Navier-Stokes (NS) equations are:

$$\rho \frac{dV}{dt} = \rho \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \rho V(\nabla \cdot V) = F - \rho \nabla p + \rho \mu \Delta V. \quad (12)$$

They are nonlinear partial differential equations, and there exists no known analytical method to solve them. Only for few simplified cases they may be solved.

For example, for the rotation Couette flow between two infinitely long concentric cylinders (radius a and b respectively) is filled with incompressible fluid, with the center line as the axis, the angular velocities are respectively Ω_1, Ω_2 , we may find the distribution of fluid motion velocity in the annular channel. The momentum equations for the r and φ directions are:

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} = \frac{u_\varphi^2}{r} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r u_\varphi) \right] = 0 \quad (14)$$

The solution of Eq.(14) is:

$$u_\varphi = Ar + \frac{B}{r} \quad (15)$$

here $A = \frac{\Omega_2 b^2 - \Omega_1 a^2}{b^2 - a^2}$, and $B = \frac{(\Omega_1 - \Omega_2) a^2 b^2}{b^2 - a^2}$.

If $b \gg a$, $B \approx 0$, $u_\varphi \approx \Omega r$. It replaces to (13),

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} = \rho \Omega^2 r \quad (16)$$

$$\text{so } p = \frac{1}{2} \rho (\Omega^2 r^2) \quad (17)$$

If velocity field $\text{rot} u = 0$, so $u = \nabla \varphi$. We obtain Laplace equation $\Delta \varphi = 0$.

Let $V_x = V_y = 0, V_x = u$, the Navier-Stokes equations (12) become to:

$$\rho u_{,t} + \rho u u_{,x} = F - \rho p_{,x} + \rho \mu u_{,xx}. \quad (18)$$

The Navier-Stokes equations (12) and (18) may be a space-time operator representation, or an energy-momentum operator representation.

If u is operator (11), the Navier-Stokes equations (18) are:

$$\begin{aligned} (-i\hbar \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t \partial x}) - \hbar^2 \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^3} = \\ F \psi - \rho \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \psi - i\mu \hbar \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^3}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

If some terms are not operator, we will obtain different equations.

Assume that $F=0$, $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x}=0$, two simplified equations are:

$$u_{,t} + u u_{,x} = \mu u_{,xx} \quad (20)$$

$$\text{And } \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t \partial x} = (\hbar \frac{1}{\rho} + \mu) \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^3} \quad (21)$$

Integral one time,

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = (\hbar \frac{1}{\rho} + \mu) \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} \quad (22)$$

It is similar to Schrödinger equation with $V=0$.

A simplified NS equation is Bernoulli equation of inviscid flow:

$$\frac{p}{\rho} + gz + \frac{V^2}{2} = \text{constant} \quad (23)$$

The corresponding Euler equation is:

$$\rho \frac{dV}{dt} = F - \rho \nabla p \quad (24)$$

The Navier-Stokes equations with a magnetic force term are:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \frac{dV}{dt} = \rho \left[\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + (V \nabla) V \right] = F + \frac{e}{c} V \\ \times B - \text{grad} p + \mu \Delta V + \frac{\eta}{3} \text{grad} \text{div} V. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

It is the well-known Alfvén equation (Alfvén & Fälthammar, 1963).

According to the Madelung's fluid mechanical model of the early quantum mechanics, let the fluid density $\rho = \psi \psi^*$, and $\psi = \sqrt{\rho} \exp(-i \text{div} V / \hbar)$, $g = \text{grad} \varphi$ we derive an equations:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{2} \hbar^2 \nabla^2 \psi + (U - Q) \psi, \quad (26)$$

where Q is a quantum potential. It is similar to the pilot-wave and the particle-wave double solution proposed de Broglie (1960).

Various Possible Developments

Hydrodynamics is similar to the electromagnetic field, in which the vortex motion $\text{rot} V \neq 0$ corresponds to the magnetic field. Generally, this corresponds to QED. Further, what general Maxwell equations are the corresponding aspects of hydrodynamics? When it develops to have a magnetic monopole, the electromagnetic fields are completely symmetric. This probably corresponds to the positive matter develops to the negative matter as unified dark matter and dark energy (Chang, 2007a, 2011, 2013a, 2017a, 2019, 2020a, 2021a, 2022a, 2023 a,b, 2024 a). For this summary we published a book *Negative*

Matter as Unified Dark Matter and Dark Energy: Its Theories and Possible Observations (Chang, 2024b).

Many small rings form quantum hydrodynamics. It corresponds to the hypercycle (Eigen & Schuster, 1979). This may be applied to turbulence, and be the relativistic hydrodynamics. It is related to superconductivity, and supercurrent, etc. The plasma is related closely to quantum hydrodynamics. Fluid dynamics may be described by the complex function, in which the correspondence is obtained from fractal to complex dimensions (Chang, 2014a). Hydrodynamics introduces the velocity potential function $\phi(x, y)$ and the flow function $\psi(x, y)$, in which the complex potential is:

$$w(z) = \phi(x, y) + i\psi(x, y) \quad (27)$$

Here $z=x+iy$. The complex velocity is $dw/dz = u - iv$.

Hydrodynamics may form various flow modes, in which some basic modes are: 1) Beeline uniform flow $w(z) = V_\infty e^{-i\alpha} z$. 2) Plane source (sink) flow $w(z) = m \ln z$. 3) Point eddy flow $w(z) = (i\Gamma / 2\pi) \ln z$. 4) Plane dipole flow $w(z) = -(m/z)$. 5) Turbulence. 6) Lorenz model. 7) Various chaotic flows, etc. They may combine various singular points and qualitative analysis theory.

Based on the universal wave-particle duality, along an opposite direction of the developed quantum mechanics, we applied a method where the wave quantities frequency ν and wave length λ are replaced on various mechanical equations, and may derive some new results. It is called the mechanical wave theory. From this we derived new operators which represent more physical quantities. Further, we proposed some nonlinear equations and their solutions, which may be probably applied to quantum theory (Chang 2014b).

An important result of hydrodynamics is to form waves, which may develop billow and tsunami, etc. Wave velocity is $c = \lambda / \tau = \omega / k$. Both

velocities of shallow water wave and deep-water wave are different. Shallow water wave agrees with soliton equation (Scott, et al. 1973). Shock wave has the continuous tangential velocity at the surface of discontinuity, which is a type of soliton.

At the same time, from Boussinesq equation and Klein-Gordon equation we may develop similarly to the nonlinear equation:

$$\phi_{tt} - \phi_{xx} = \sigma(\phi^2)_{xx} + \phi_{xxxx} \quad (28)$$

For this a solution is (Scott, et al. 1973; Taniuti & Nishihara, 1983):

$$\phi(x, t) = \frac{1}{4} k^2 \operatorname{sech}^2 \left[\frac{1}{2} (kx - \beta t + \delta) \right] \quad (29)$$

Here $\beta^2 = k^2 + k^4$.

The equation of hydrodynamics is:

$$m \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + \nabla \left(\frac{1}{2} m v^2 \right) - (m v \times \operatorname{rot} v) = F - \frac{m}{\rho} \operatorname{grad} p. \quad (30)$$

Suppose that the force in liquid possesses potential, so $F = -\nabla U$. When this is extended to wave, since the wave velocity is changeable, and wave has kinetic energy, and has also potential energy. If $(m v^2 / 2) + U = E = h \nu$, the equation (30) will become:

$$h \frac{\partial k}{\partial t} + h \nabla v = h k \times \operatorname{rot} v - V \operatorname{grad} p \quad (31)$$

Here $V = h \nu / c^2 \rho$ is a volume. The known light pressure is $p = (1 + \gamma) N h \nu / c$, here γ is a reflectance, and then a complete similar wave

pressure should be:

$$p = (1 + \gamma)P \quad (32)$$

Therefore, Eq.(31) becomes:

$$\frac{\partial k}{\partial t} + \nabla v = k \times \text{rot} v - \frac{h v}{\rho c^2} (1 + \gamma) \text{grad} |k|. \quad (33)$$

Perhaps, this may be called the hydrodynamics of wave. For the irrotational wave, $\text{rot} v = 0$.

This should be the extensive quantum theory (Chang,2002,2013b,2018,2024c), and be general Schrödinger equation, which may be unified fermions and bosons (Chang,2023c). The time-independent Schrödinger equation is:

$$\Delta \psi + \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} (E - V) \psi = 0 \quad (34)$$

Let $\frac{2m}{\hbar^2} (E - V) = k^2$, Eq.(34) becomes to the Helmholtz equation, i.e., wave equation:

$$\nabla^2 \psi + k^2 \psi = 0 \quad (35)$$

When $V=E$, it is Laplace equation.

In spherical coordinates, by general method let $\psi = R(r)Y(\theta, \varphi) = R(r)\Theta(\theta)\Phi(\varphi)$, and $x=kr$, $y(x) = \sqrt{x}R(r)$, so

$$x^2 \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} + x \frac{dy}{dx} + [x^2 - (j + \frac{1}{2})^2] y = 0 \quad (36)$$

It is $j+(1/2)$ order Bessel equation. In column coordinates, by general method let $\psi = R(\rho)Z(z)\Phi(\varphi)$, and $x = \sqrt{k^2 - h^2} \rho$, $R=y$, so

$$x^2 \frac{d^2 R}{dx^2} + x \frac{dR}{dx} + [x^2 - m^2] R = 0 \quad (37)$$

$R(x)$ is m order Bessel equation, which is also discussed by Weinberg (2015). If quantized $j+(1/2)$ and m are all spins, Eqs.(36) and (37) will correspond to fermions and bosons, respectively (Chang,2023c).

The Dirac equations and Klein-Gordon equations are all the free particle equations. For the interaction it must develop, such as in the electromagnetic field. If there is an interaction, it can be divided into strong and weak interactions, etc. For example, the potential V is (Chang, 2014a)

$$E^2 = (cp)^2 + m^2 c^4 + V^2 \quad (38)$$

$$\text{and } E = \alpha cp + \beta mc^2 + \gamma \mathcal{W} \quad (39)$$

Such Euler equation is:

$$F = \rho \frac{dV}{dt} = -\nabla p - \rho \nabla \Phi \quad (40)$$

Here Φ is gravity potential.

Applications of Fluid Mechanics and Quantum Fluid Mechanics

Because continuum is very common, fluid mechanics is universal and is widely used in many aspects. Moreover, the general hydrodynamic equations are nonlinear, which is related to soliton, fractal, and chaos, etc. The well-known basic equations of hydrodynamics include the Navier-Stokes equations and Lorenz

equations, which is origin of meteorology (Lorenz, 1963).

In particle physics in 1953 Landau proposed a hydrodynamic model. In 1968 C.N. Yang, et al., proposed the limit fragmentation model, i. e. the coherent droplet model, etc.

Beale, Kato and Majda proposed a theorem: When $t \rightarrow T$, the curl $(u(x, t))$ will grow so fast that the integrals will diverge. When t is close to T , the direction of the vorticity vector changes with x , and rotates. This should be related to the turbulence.

A very small friction coefficient for the NS equation will also produce larger energy dissipation. This is probably: 1. Time effect, 2. chaos.

Applications in Biology

The biological hydrodynamics is known, especially for blood and the circulation systems (Burton, 1965; Rushmer, 1970; Caro, et al. 1978; Volkenstein, 1982). Torre and Cifre (2020) searched hydrodynamic properties of biomacromolecules and macromolecular.

Grabsch, et al. (2024), discussed from particle currents to tracer diffusion as universal correlation profiles in single-file dynamics. Yuan and Tanaka (2024a,b) researched hydrodynamic effects on the collapse kinetics of flexible polyelectrolytes, and impact of hydrodynamic interactions on the kinetic pathway of protein folding. Yariv, et al. (2024), searched hydrodynamic interactions between rough surfaces. Bioclogging is a complex process that involves various coupled mechanisms such as hydrodynamics and particle properties. Desclaux, et al. (2024), explored bioclogging at the microscale level, and developed a highly sensitive method to precisely measure small flow rates with a low response time.

For general cases, this must combine the extensive quantum biology (Change, 2012a,b), in which from bio-macromolecules and cells to any biological individuality are all extensive quantum. Based on the extensive quantum biology, we proposed that Schrödinger equation at column coordinates and its solution may derive the double helical structure of DNA. It is

necessity mathematical conclusion that quantum mechanics has symmetry (Chang, 2014c, 2015, 2022b).

Applications in Astronomy

A main movement in astronomy is the ring, and the Kepler-Newton motion of gravity. Philosophical thought is theory of vortex (whirlpool) of Descartes. An important foundation of astrophysics is fluid mechanics, which corresponds to the nebula.

It is applied to galaxies and the disk dynamics and spiral structures, and may derive the rotation curve of Mestel disk and the rotation curve of exponential disk, etc (Binney & Tremaine, 1987). This is similar to aerodynamics, and corresponds to the cosmical electrodynamics (Alfven & Falthammar, 1963).

Alexeev (2015) in Chapter 11 “Astrophysical Applications” considered the principle of the universal antigravitation from positions of the Newtonian theory of gravitation and non-local kinetic theory. It is found that explanation of the Hubble effect in the universe and peculiar features of the rotational speeds of galaxies need not in introduction of new essence like dark matter and dark energy. The origin of difficulties consists in total Oversimplification following from principles of local physics and reflects the general shortcomings of the local kinetic transport theory.

Based on the basic equations of a rotating disk on the nebula, we applied the qualitative analysis theory of nonlinear equation, and obtained a nonlinear dynamical model of formation of binary stars (Chang, 2000). Under certain conditions a pair of singular points results in the course of evolution, which corresponds to the binary stars. Under other conditions these equations give a single central point, which corresponds to a single star. This method and model may be extended and developed. Further, based on the hydrodynamics and hydromagnetics of nebula, from the NS equations (12) and Alfver equation of the cosmical electrodynamics we discussed the formation of binary stars by the qualitative

analysis theory. The nonlinear interaction and rotation play very crucial roles (Chang, 2007b).

Using the nonlinear equations of hydrodynamics we researched the formation of the binary and multiple stars (Chang, 2000,2007b,2013c). In the two-dimensional plane, the nonlinear hydrodynamic equations (25) become:

$$\frac{\partial \rho u}{\partial t} = -(u \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial}{\partial y}) \rho u + F_x + \frac{e}{c} B_z v - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \mu (\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}) u + \frac{\eta}{3} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}), \quad (41)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho v}{\partial t} = -(u \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial}{\partial y}) \rho v + F_y - \frac{e}{c} B_z u - \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \mu (\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}) v + \frac{\eta}{3} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}). \quad (42)$$

For the simplified equations, its characteristic equation is

$$\lambda^2 - T\lambda + D = 0 \quad (43)$$

A plane system has usually three singular points. For general cases: 1) When $D < 0$, a corresponding singular point is a saddle point. 2) When $D > 0$, the point is a focal point if $\Delta < 0$, or a nodal point if $\Delta > 0$. 3) When $T < 0$, the point is a stable sink. For $T > 0$, the point is an unstable source.

Based on the Lorenz model derived from the equations of hydrodynamics of nebula, we discussed the formation of binary stars by the qualitative analysis theory of nonlinear equation. In the Lorenz model the two wings form just the binary stars, whose Roche surface is result of evolution under certain condition (Chang, 2007b,2013c). The base of the most exact evolutionary theory of large scale structures is the general relativity, whose 2+1 dimensional plane equations of gravitational field are calculated. Based on these equations, we

discussed the evolutions of disk nebula by the qualitative analysis theory, in which the binary stars or single star are formed for different conditions. This is the most exact model of formation of binary stars. The nonlinear interaction plays a crucial role, and is necessary condition of the formation of binary stars and of multiple stars (Chang, 2013c).

The density wave theory is also based on fluid mechanics (Lin, et al.1964,1969). Based on the nonlinear equations of density wave theory, the evolutionary direction and the observable conditions on spiral galaxies may be derived by the qualitative analysis theory. According to new observations, it can be proved quantitatively that a mode of eight major planets of the Solar System is a symmetrical structure: four terrestrial planets and the asteroid belt; four Jovian planets and the Kuiper belt (including Pluto) (Chang, 2014d).

A dipole or a doublet may develop to the positive-negative dipole. It is a huge extensive quantum theory. Chandell, et al. (2024), discussed evaporation of active drops as puncturing drops and particle deposits of ring galaxy patterns. Further, a dipole or a doublet may develop to the positive-negative dipole (Chang, 2024a). It will be a huge extensive quantum theory.

Circulation is $\Gamma = \oint_C V dl$, vorticity is circulation per unit area. Stream function ψ (only for two dimensional flows) and velocity potential form an orthogonal grid system in flow field. Their basic solutions are the uniform flow, source, sink, free or potential vortex and so on.

Based on the characteristics of sunspots, we proposed the nonlinear chaos model of sunspot, which is similar Lorenz butterfly. Further, some cases of sunspot are discussed by the qualitative analysis theory of the nonlinear equations. Moreover, this model and method of sunspot may be corrected and developed from astrophysics and mathematics, for example, it may combine the general magnetic field model of sunspot (Chang, 2021b).

Base of sunspot is the solar magnetic field, in which the magnetohydrodynamics equations are similar to the Lorenz model (Lorenz, 1963):

$$dx/dt = -vx + ky \quad (44)$$

$$dy/dt = ax - by - xz \quad (45)$$

$$dz/dt = -cz + xy \quad (46)$$

This result is a space mode. Usually, we suppose that all parameters are positive. Let $v=k$, $b=1$, when $a>1$, Lorenz equations have two stable solutions:

$$x_s = y_s = \pm(a-1)^{1/2}, z_s = a-1 \quad (47)$$

They have a critical value $a_c = \frac{k(k+c+3)}{k-c-1}$.

When $a/a_c > 1$, the solution becomes unstable. When $a/a_c = 1.3$, $k=4$, x , y and z change with time period. When $a/a_c = 1.3$, $k=10$, it is not periodicity, and is chaotic randomness; $k=200$, with periodicity (Swinney & Gollub, 1981; Tritton, 1988). In a word, the nonlinear equations have sensitivity to initial conditions.

If various parameters in Eqs.(44)(45)(46) take suitable values, a beautiful Lorenz strange attractor (Fig.1) will be obtained.

Figure 1. Lorenz Strange Attractor

The butterfly diagram of the sunspot corresponds to chaos. Add the timeline T , and we can obtain the period $T=11$ years cycle (Fig.2).

Figure 2. Period and Butterfly Diagram of Sunspot

In astronomy Alfvén (1981) researched systematically the cosmic plasma. It includes the duality of magnetic field and electric current, which corresponds just to general fluid dynamics and magnetohydrodynamics, and sunspot.

Applications in Geosciences

Geosciences include various levels: Earth core, mantle, lithosphere, hydrosphere, atmospheric sphere, and biosphere. These levels are closely related and interact with each other (Christopherson, 1997; Tarbuck & Lutgens, 1998; Hamblin & Christiansen, 1998). Some levels are liquids or gases, and have various cycles, such as atmospheric circulation (Kump, et al.1999), ocean circulation (Hartmann, 1994), etc. The ocean has El Niño phenomena, and the periodic reversal of the geomagnetic field and so on.

Based on general geodynamics (Turcotte & Schubert, 1982) and the Gutenberg-Richter (GR) relation, we proposed the magnitude-period formula of the earthquake (Chang, 1989, 1997):

$$T = 10^{(a_0 - a) - (b_0 M_0 - bM)} T_0 \quad (48)$$

and its simplified formula:

$$T = 10^{-b(M_0-M)} T_0. \quad (49)$$

Further, based on the nonlinear equations of fluid dynamics in Earth's crust with momentum conservation, from the NS equations (12) we obtained a chaos equation, in which chaos corresponds to the earthquake, and shows complexity on seismology. But, combining the Burridge-Knopoff block-and-spring model of an earthquake fault presented by Carlson, Langer, et al. (1989a,b, 1991a,b, 1994), a simplified nonlinear solution and corresponding magnitude-period formula (49) of earthquakes may be derived approximately (Chang, 1997,2012c,2017b,2021c). From these theories some predictions can be calculated quantitatively and are already tested.

From 2004 to 2017, according to the formula (49) we predicted future earthquakes will take place in 2009, 2014 and 2019 in California, and large earthquake of 2019 as intersection of two series of earthquakes will be more possible (Chang, 2012c). Then earthquakes (M=6.9) occurred on 3 August of 2009, and M=6 on 24 August of 2014. In 2019 California occurred two bigger earthquakes on 4 July M=6.4 and 5 July M=7.1. This shows that earthquakes may be predicted initially, and be calculated simply. Therefore, President of World Institute for Scientific Exploration, Dr. John H. Reed, said: "I was very impressed with your prediction of the earthquake that occurred in July in California. This certainly shows how powerful your earthquake prediction model is."

Combining the Lorenz nonlinear model with two "wings", we researched the earthquake migration to and fro, and two or a few time series on earthquakes in the same region (Robinson, et al. 2001; Gerstenberger, et al. 2005; Chang, 2012c,2017b,2021c). If various modern scientific instruments, different scientific theories and some paranormal ways for earthquake are combined each other, the accuracy of multilevel prediction will be

increased (Chang, 2017b,2021c). Moreover, we proposed the nonlinear whole seismology and its three basic laws, and researched the topological seismology.

The magnitude-period formula of the earthquake (49) extends to complex numbers:

$$T_0 10^{-b(M_0-M)} \Rightarrow T_0 e^{i\theta} = T_0 (\cos \theta + i \sin \theta) \quad (50)$$

It is also a function with two periods.

Based on the many levels and their cycles in geoscience, we researched the hypercycle on geoscience. This is the hypercycle as a tool of self-organization applied to geoscience. It may form from a level to the next higher level. These levels influence each other and the co-evolution. Further, we discussed some possible mathematical methods, which include graph, vector, matrix, some equations, similar theories, etc. This method can be developed and perfected (Chang, 2023d).

It is known that there are three types of crustal stress environments forming sedimentary basins: the maximum stress axis is a vertical tensile basin, and the axis is a horizontal shrinkage and shear basin. And various plate-tectonic environments of these configurations are discussed (Allen & Allen, 1990; Miall, 1990). Based on the island mass effect, Messié, et al. (2022), researched basin-scale biogeochemical and ecological impacts of islands in the tropical Pacific Ocean.

When the earth changes from liquid to solid (soft matter), it forms a continent. Based on the hydrodynamics in geosciences, we may research formation of basin and hydrocarbon layer and energy belt due to rotation. In this case, the lighter biological residue deposits around the basin, and forms a coal-oil-gas energy belt. It originates possibly from the circulation of the fluid, and is probably coupled with the magnetic field. Different layers are formed with the different density-viscosity coefficient. The formation of basin supposes approximately an

axis symmetric. The most simplified is that the basin has a rotating circular motion as a plane. The centrifugal force is:

$$\Omega \times (\Omega \times r) = \Omega^2 r \quad (51)$$

If Ω are the same, the fluid motion speed not only will change with the distance, but also vary with the density, viscosity, and resistance. This can be simulated by computer.

Applications in Social Sciences

The basis of the social public opinion should be the social thermodynamics and the social hydrodynamics. It includes the social combustion theory, and the social shock wave theory and the entropy of social action theory (Niu, 2009).

Using the nonlinear equations of hydrodynamics (25) we may research the formulations of the binary and multiple centers in various social systems from public opinion, party to market, city, etc (Chang, 2013f). Here μ and η correspond to some resistances in a social field.

We discussed social field and social dynamics, and researched systematically the social hydrodynamics as example of nonlinear whole sociology, which is a macroscopic and whole description on sociology. This may include various social flows (matter flows, energy flows, information flows, biologic flows, virus flows, and money flows, commodity flows, brand flows, culture flows, music flows, even global fluid, terrorism and its growth, etc). When various fluids form different patterns, we discussed the social geography. For example, much flows are collected, and form city, it is an attractor and basin. Peers, magnates, dignitaries, and high science-technology form peaks in different regions. It may describe equalitarianism, despotism, oligarch, etc.

Based on the principles and mechanism of the social hydrodynamics, an important result of hydrodynamics is to form waves, and social waves may form various social tides. We discussed social justice and various defects as

social crises. The social hydrodynamics and corresponding waves and tides may describe positive social progress and various negative social crises from mathematical and physical mechanism and methods (Chang, 2014e, 2017c). Religion fluid will change distribution of belief in some regions, for instance, Islam in Europe. Further, social hydrodynamics may develop to social magnetohydrodynamics, and social general relativity (Chang, 2014e), etc.

Everyone possesses fate and luck. General relativity shows that matter and movement determine the space-time of everyone. This as a universal physical representation of causality is a great contribution to modern social science, we proposed the social extensive general relativity, which may describe some evolutionary orbits of life and society (Chang, 2014e, 2020b, 2024d). In social hydrodynamics some keys are velocity, tension, viscosity, resistance, and pathway, space-time. It may form turbulence, chaos, emergence, etc., and produce various social movements, social regulations and social order. Papastergiadis (2000) researched the turbulence of migration. Global Sea and global fluids produce globalization, shrinking world, global village and panhumanity (Frankling, et al. 2000).

We should increase velocity of positive energy, and research to form the origin of various tides of new science-technology, of democracy and peace, and form the equal network society, so that promote social progress and developments. According to third law of the nonlinear theory of economic growth, i.e., the economic growth mode transition and new developed period law (Chang, 2013e), further development of social economy must exploits new merchandise and market, and adjust output configuration, and reform technique, and train personnel, so that boost up the immanence ability of social development and the international competitiveness. The society should reform continuously to achieve a higher seedtime, i.e., search new economic growth point for microeconomics. Contrarily, the social hydrodynamics may describe various negative social crises. We should avoid and check the sources of various social crises, and decrease diffusion velocity of crises, and reduce the height

of shock waves. Positive ways are increase flow flux, and negative ways are increase viscosity and resistance, even build breakwater.

Social hydrodynamics passes through nonlinear mechanism to derive social chaos, which obtains social storm, for example, the drastic change of the East European countries, Arab Spring, many waves on freedom- democracy, network, information society, and so on. Russel, et al., discussed three-wave coupled equations, whose fractal dimension $D=2.32$ (Russel, et al. 1980). In Iraq and Syria many forces converge to arouse that war becomes chaos and turbulence.

Social hydrodynamics may extend to the social quantum hydrodynamics. In graphical description of fluid motion, a pathline corresponds to the course of life. In the social field, the steady flow corresponds to normal material flow, personnel flow, capital flow, etc.; the unsteady flow corresponds to unsteady abnormal material flow, personnel flow, capital flow, etc. In generally case the conservations of matter, energy and momentum are satisfied. People and certain substances, funds are incompressible. But, there are many branches of flows in multiple topological economics and sociology (Chang, 2013e,2020b,2023e), and the larger the pipes, the more normal capital, the more material loss.

These similar fluids can use hydrodynamics or general relativity, and may derive periodicity. Cycle stability is the biological and physiological characteristics, sunspots, etc. Cycle instability corresponds to earthquakes, social-political phenomena, etc. We proposed the shipboard wave theory. In social fields any things like the regular boats in time-river, they cannot but arose waves. Based on the rules and theory of wave, we may forecast moving direction and velocity, and estimate their effects. It is a causality of social hydrodynamics.

The separation and resistance, the lift in flow can be used in the social field, and correspond to the separation and ability of the social class and other aspects, such as the rise and fall of the position. Resistance is mainly determined by the viscosity. The Bernoulli theorem can derive the Kutta-Zhukovsky lift theorem:

$$F \approx -\rho u_0 \Gamma_l, \text{ and } \Gamma_l = \oint u dl \quad (52)$$

This is also adapted to the lift of the rotating object.

In sociology, Eq.(9) quantitatively indicates that the social groups further away from the center of power are more marginalized, and the less interest advantage.

The initial conditions and boundary conditions (corresponding to nature and nurture respectively) are different, especially when the Reynolds number is large. Reynolds number is smaller, the greater the equal opportunity. When the temperature difference increases to a certain threshold, there will be Benard convection, social class changes, exchanges, and revolution. A vortex is a cycle without moving forward. But, vorticity can also change the positive and negative signs, and the viscosity produces a vorticity.

Based on the synergetics (Haken, 1983), we proposed the social synergetics and the four basic theorems (Chang, 2013e). From the synergetic equations, we obtained the equations on the rule of law, and may prove mathematically that a society of the rule of law cannot lack any aspect for three types of the legislation, the administration and the judicature. From synergetics we obtained the Lorenz model, whose social meaning is a visualized two-party mechanism as a type of stable structure in democracy. It shows that when the social-field strength as an order parameter achieves a certain threshold, a type of stable self-organized structure in democracy can be formed from chaos and synergetics. A developed direction of society is the combination from macroscopic to microscopic order, from an actual capable handling to an ideal pursuance.

We proposed an equation of corruption, and discussed quantitatively some threshold values for a social system into corruption (Chang, 2013d). First the bifurcation with two periods appears, and finally, the solution will achieve chaos, namely, whole social system will decompose and become confusion. From

quantitative value of bifurcation-chaos, we may estimate that if the corruption members in any system or a certain level attain to 37.5%, a dangerous double periodic bifurcation will appear. If the members attain to 0.70057759...=70%, this system as whole will show an incurable dark. It is represented visually in a known figure from bifurcation to chaos (Fig.3). The bifurcation-chaos seems to correspond to flow from layer to turbulence.

Figure 3. Bifurcation-Chaos Diagram

Conclusion

Fluid mechanics is a universal theory. We research the new quantum fluid mechanics by operator method, and discuss its various developments combined the extensive quantum theory and other theories. Further, we search possible applications in some aspects, which include biology, astronomy, geosciences, and some social sciences, etc.

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